

Women Self- Help Groups in the Empowerment of Women

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Abstract

There is an increasing realization of the vital role of women in the emerging modern society. In this concern, the empowerment of women is urgent need for bringing about sustainable development at a faster pace. The year 2001 is proclaimed as Women's Empowerment year. Formation of Women Self Help Groups (WSHG) plays a remarkable role in the advancement and emancipation of women from all the social taboos and economic barriers. Women's Self Help groups have been created and effectively used for empowering women in many developmental programmes like Mahila samakhya, Rajasthan Women's Development project, Tamil Nadu Women's Development Project, Women in Agriculture Project, and Integrated Women's Empowerment and Development project in Haryana. The paper attempts to focus attention on the origin, growth of Women Self Help Groups in Tamil Nadu and their developmental activities in empowering the women towards social equilibrium in the socio-economic fronts.

The present paper has highlighted the role of Women Self Help groups in the empowerment of women through the means of economic power. The study views that the role of women self help groups for the improvement of economic status of the women in the society has contributing to increase income, employment opportunities, makes women self help group members economically self reliant and more self confident. The women self help groups provides economic security, self-confidence, decision making power to their members and in such a way they contribute for the socio-economic and political changes. Thus the WSHG members actively participate in the empowerment of women with the sole aim of promoting the interest of the rural women-folk.

Introduction

There is an increasing realization of the vital role of women in the emerging modern society. In this concern, the empowerment of women is urgent need for bringing about sustainable development at a faster pace. The year 2001 is proclaimed as Women's Empowerment year. Formation of Women Self Help Groups (WSHG) plays a remarkable role in the advancement and emancipation of women from all the social taboos and economic barriers. Women's Self Help groups have been created and effectively used for empowering women in many developmental programmes like Mahila samakhya, Rajasthan Women's Development project, Tamil Nadu Women's Development Project, Women in Agriculture Project, and Integrated Women's Empowerment and Development project in Haryana. The paper attempts to focus attention on the origin, growth of Women

Self Help Groups in Tamil Nadu and their developmental activities in empowering the women towards social equilibrium in the socio-economic fronts.

The Government of Tamil Nadu during the period between 1991 and 1996 undertook an important step through guiding principles for policy frame in the sphere of women's advancement by protecting and promoting the equality of women in the society. According to the new policy initiative on women, known as "Vision 2006 Policy for Advancement of Women in Tamil Nadu" each and every project and programme in Tamil Nadu was decided to increase the status of women in the society. One such a programme which gaining much support of Government of Tamil Nadu is 'Self Help Group', which ensures the socio-economic empowerment of the rural poor.¹

Among the various aspects of women empowerment like economic, political, cultural, educational and legal, the economic empowerment is considered to be the most vital empowerment of all the aspects. Hence an attempt is made in this paper to focus attention on the role of Women Self Help Groups in empowering women for their economic well-being.

Government's Interest in Women's Welfare

Both State and Central Government have interest in the welfare of the women. With the dawn of independence this attitude of the Government has taken a new shape and Social Welfare Programmes are receiving more and more attention in the Five Year Plans. The First Five Year plan made a humble beginning with this important programme with an outlay of four crores. In the Second plan provision was increased to rupees nineteen crores. In the Third Five Year plan, the allocation was rupees thirty one crores including an amount of three crores provided for Child Welfare Programme. Out of this, rupees nineteen crores were in the Central Sector and rupees twelve crores in the State Sector. In the Fourth Five Year Plan, an amount of rupees fifty crores has been earmarked for Social Welfare Programme. In that amount, rupees thirteen crores have been provided for Central Social Welfare Board Programmes, one crore for adult education and nearly rupees three crores for nutrition programme for the children of 0-3 age groups. The important thing to be noted is not the amount of money earmarked for Social Welfare Programmes in the Five year Plans but the physiological change that has been brought about amongst the social workers and the community at large.

The important schemes sanctioned by the Social Welfare Department under the Five Year Plans are Service Homes, Working Women's Hostels, Pre-Schools and Integrated Child Welfare Demonstration Project.

Empowerment of Women

The word 'empowerment' has been given currency by UN agencies during the recent years.² What it really means is simple. Over the centuries, commensurate with the role that they perform, women have not been given their due place in history as well as in social and economic life. One of the objectives of education, it is argued, therefore, should be devise strategies and processes through which the role of women is given its due importance. In other words, their identity as one-half of humanity and the role they perform must be recognized. Until very recently that had not happened and this is precisely what requires to be ensured now.³

'Women Empowerment' is a new term in the area of women development. In its widest sense it implies development of women's life in every aspect. The basic objective of women empowerment is nothing but understanding of one's potential not only for self-development but also for the benefit of the society as a whole. It involves five major components such as economic independence, knowledge, awareness, participation, self image and autonomy. It also clearly emphasizes the fact that the empowerment of women is a much wider task to be achieved.⁴

Empowerment of women was one of the primary objectives of the ninth plan. It made an effort to create an environment where women can freely exercise their rights both within and outside home as equal partners along with men.⁵ The term empowerment is often used to describe a process whereby the powerless or disempowered gain a greater share of control of resources and decision making.⁶

It is believed that economic strength is the basis of social, political and psychological power in the society. Thus the lower status of women mostly stems from their low economic status and subsequent dependence and lack of decision –making power. Therefore, if women gain economic strength, they gain visibility and voice.

Among the various approaches, the empowerment approach in development programmes is considered best. This approach is modeled to ‘power’ itself and gain control over the self, the resources and freedom to decide. This process of gaining control over the self, the resources and decision making power may be termed as empowerment. Ideally, the empowerment process should aim at “women finding time and space of their own” and should provide mechanisms for their active participation in the development process. Further it should ensure their role in decision-making and should foster self-reliance both socially and economically. Facilitating their direct participation in income generation activities and decision making –making capacity can make significant contributions towards women empowerment. This will enable to take initiatives for their development into their own hands. Through a well-directed package of skill enhancement, credit facilities and educational inputs, women can discover their economic role and gain recognition in the society.

Entrepreneurship can help women’s economic independence and improve their social status. Automatically the women get empowered once they attain economic independence. The development of women entrepreneurship enables society to understand and appreciate their abilities. It enhances their status and leads to integration of women in nation building and economic development. It provides the needed psychological satisfaction and imbibes a deep sense of achievement to create their enhanced identity in society.⁷

Micro Finance: Self- Help Groups: Women Empowerment

Women are the most efficient route to end hunger and poverty. As per 1991 census, work participation rate of women is 22%. This statistics reveal that women require the special attention of the development activities and there is urgent need for the promotion of women entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurship is a more suitable profession for women than regular employment in public and private sectors since they have to fulfill dual roles. The emergence of self help group is a welcome development for empowerment of women. Women empowerment is critical to the socio-economic progress of the community and bringing women into the mainstream of national development has, therefore, been a major concern of the Government. The Ministry of Rural Development has special components for women in its programme and funds are earmarked as “Women’s Component” to ensure flow of adequate sources for the same. There are hundreds of women whose lives have been radically transformed by the ‘micro finance’ or ‘Income Generation’ programme. The dignity that comes with financial independence has brought about important changes in the surrounding villages.⁸

Tamil Nadu Women Development Project

The objective of the Tamil Nadu Women Development Project is capacity building, socio empowerment and economic empowerment of poor women

1. Capacity Building and Economic Empowerment

1. Savings habit has been inculcated. Credit and thrift practice is being motivated.
2. The influence of money is totally weeded out
3. Internal lending is promoted to meet the consumption needs.
4. Lineages with banks and repayment rate is very appreciable.
5. Convergence with various departments is facilitated. (Banks / Rural Development / TAHDCO etc

2. Social Empowerment

1. Health and sanitation of women has improved.
2. The SHG movement has made an effective role against the social evils like prevention of child labour, female infanticide and dowry problem etc.
3. SHG women participate actively in Grama Sabha Meetings and Town Panchayat level meetings.
4. The power of collective bargaining has increased through the SHG movement.
5. Through the SHGs movement casteism is abolished and secular society is being emerged.

The members of SHG are involved in various activities like food processing, coir industry, handloom, jute products and service sector industries etc., and have emerged into micro-entrepreneurs with sufficient marketing backup. This SHG movement silently brought about a revolution in the life of women at large.

3. Income Substituting Activities

Majority of the rural women with the marginal exceptions of the rich and higher caste groups, participate in income substituting activities or to put appropriately cost saving activities. For example, those belonging to the poorer strata, a particularly the landless spend considerable amount of time in fetching water, collecting fuel, processing grains, sewing clothes, repairing houses, caring for small animals and poultry. On the other hand, those belonging to farm households spend considerable time in activities like cleaning, drying processing the grain for seed in the farm in addition to requirements of family consumption, kitchen gardens, and dairying and poultry activities. However this type of contribution continued to be considered invisible, as none of these are treated as work by most of the economists and statisticians.⁹

Women Self Help Groups in Tamil Nadu

On 9th December 1983 the Government established Tamil Nadu Corporation for Development of Women Limited (TNCDW) under the Companies Act of 1956. Its registered office is located in Chennai while its area of operation extends to the entire State of Tamil Nadu. It is to promote the development of women in fields like education, family welfare, empowerment etc. Its objectives are

1. to build up the capacity of poor and disadvantaged women in order that they are enable to cross all socio-economic barriers.
2. to achieve the equality of status of poor women as participants, decision makers and beneficiaries.
3. to empower women to work together with men as equal partners and to inspire a new generation of women.
4. to promote and ensure the human rights of women at all stages of their life cycle.
5. to advocate changes in government policies and programmes in favour of disadvantaged women and

6. to enable poor women to participate fully and actively in decision –making in the family, community and at the local, state and national levels.¹⁰ The Corporation implements the schemes for the socio- economic upliftment of women throughout Tamil Nadu. Some of the schemes are:

1. Tamil Nadu Women’s Development Project (Mahalir Thittam)
2. Assistance for formation of 25000 Self Help Groups.
3. World Bank assisted Tamil Nadu Empowerment and poverty Reduction Project.

One of the avowed objectives of Government of Tamil Nadu is to help women to improve income levels through training and development and better employment opportunities and helping in the designing of labour saving devices that will reduce the drudgery of daily chores of women.

To achieve the proposed objective the Government of Tamil Nadu under J.Jayalalithaa had started Women Self Help Groups in the year 1992. The main purpose se of Women Self Help Groups is to develop economical position, to ensure socio-political empowerment of the rural poor. The WSHG has consistently growing membership and as on 2003 it has 1,26, 106 groups containing 21,50,193 women members and they have the deposit savings of 288 crores ¹¹ and as on 27th August 2005, the membership has crossed thirty –five lakhs and forty –two thousand in two lakh and twenty five thousand Self help Groups. The WSGH have mobilized a saving of rupees 754 crores. The financing of the SHG programme is shared between the centre and the State on a 75: 25 ratio. The State Government was only fulfilling its duty in helping the SHG movement to increase its breadth and scope.¹²

Tamil Nadu Women Development Project and Swarna Jayanthi Gram SwarozgarYojana (SGSY) Scheme implemented by the Rural development Department have been converged for Rural Self help groups. Similarly, in respect of Self -Help groups in urban areas , Swarna Jayanthi Shehari Roagar Yojana (SJSRY) and Tamil Nadu Women development Project are being operated in a converged manner.¹³

The Government is supporting and motivating women from families below poverty line to join Self Help groups and shall achieve the plan of converging another fifteen lakhs women over the next three years. A sum of rupees twenty crores has been provided under Mahalir Thittam for the year 2005-2006 to improve the quality of life of women.¹⁴ The present status of women in India is determined to a considerable extent by her employment position, as observed by a number of scholars in the field of gender studies; economic independence and higher social position are two major motivational factors for the women to go for gainful employment in the present society.

To sum up, the present paper has highlighted the role of Women Self Help groups in the empowerment of women through the means of economic power. The study views that the role of women self help groups for the improvement of economic status of the women in the society has contributing to increase income, employment opportunities, makes women self help group members economically self reliant and more self confident. The women self help groups provides economic security, self – confidence, decision making power to their members and in such a way they contribute for the socio-economic and political changes. Thus the WSHG members actively participate in the empowerment of women with the sole aim of promoting the interest of the rural women–folk.

End Notes

1. Quest Historica, (Journal of History), Vol.IV, No.2, Rajapalyam, October 2005, p.82.
2. Tribune, 13 July 1988.
3. Mahajan , V.S., (ed.)Women’s Contribution to India’s Economic and Social Development, New Delhi, 1989, p.337.

4. Razia Parvin M., Empowerment of Women : Strategies and Struggles for Social Justice, New Delhi, 2005, pp.1-2.
5. Aruna Goel, Organisation and Structure of Women development and Empowerment , New Delhi, 2004, pp.24-26.
6. Razia Parvin , M., op.cit., pp.70-74.
7. Sundararaj, T., Research Papers on Trends in Higher Education and Formation of Ideology, Identity and Collective Consciousness (1835-1986), Tiruchirappalli, 2005, p.49.
8. Amirtha Jothi, C., 'A Profile of Rural Women In Tamil Nadu and Their Role in Economic Development' in Proceedings of the Eleventh Annual Session of Tamil Nadu History Congress, Kanchipuram, 2004, p.87.
9. Ibid., 87-88.
10. Tamilnadu Corporation for Development of Women Ltd, Dawn of New Hope, Chennai, No Year, p.1.
11. Tamil Arasu, November 2003, p.43.
12. Ibid., pp.45-47.
13. The Hindu, 27 August 2005; Kalaikathir, 26 August 2005, p.8.
14. Quest Historica, p.84.